

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF VOLLEYBALL SPECIALISTS IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article aims to improve the professional and pedagogical skills of volleyball specialists in the field of physical education, to improve the qualifications of pedagogical personnel - based on the State educational standards for the types of education, which ensures the continuous growth of professional and pedagogical skills, and the educational process is carried out at a high scientific and methodological level. and it is emphasized that it is necessary to regularly update professional knowledge, qualifications and skills in the taught subject or course, pedagogical or information technologies and interactive methods of teaching.*

Keywords: *physical education, volleyball, specialization, professional pedagogical skills, advanced modern experience, biological, psychological, information technologies, creativity, innovation, reproduction, adaptation, local model.*

INTRODUCTION. Today, physical education and sports, like all areas of development of our country, are developing within the priority directions of state policy. Adoption of the Law "On Physical Education and Sports", Decision "On Measures for the Further Development of Physical Education and Sports in Uzbekistan", Decisions "On Further Strengthening Public Sports Events" and other conceptual documents related to this field, their gradual implementation is being implemented and the special emphasis on physical education and sports in the Laws of the Constitution of Uzbekistan "On Education" and "National Program of Personnel Training" is an expression of the above-mentioned opinion. The practical product of these documents is that Uzbek sports have been glorifying the fame of our country in front of the world community with its high results in recent years, the construction of thousands of sports complexes that meet international standards, and the fact that the most prestigious international competitions are held in different regions of our country. But not to miss high results, training of qualified, competitive athletes is directly related to training of young talented reserves.

According to The President of Uzbekistan Sh., M. Mirziyoev's Resolution No. 2909 of "On measures to further develop the higher education system" approved on April 20, 2017 is dedicated. According to this decision, the goal is to radically improve the higher education system, to fundamentally revise the content of personnel training in accordance with the priority tasks of the socio-economic development of our country, and to create the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists at the level of international standards. In the decision, special importance is attached to the work on improving the qualifications of pedagogues and scientific personnel by introducing advanced international experience into the educational process in the higher education system, establishing close cooperation relations with leading foreign scientific and educational institutions, and it is also noted that they are not being carried out at the level of demand.

In the tasks and work activities of a physical education teacher, he is mainly a multifaceted specialist, he educates the growing young generation to be physically healthy and mature, in middle school, high school and higher educational institutions, in the armed forces, he gives them knowledge and skills together with physical education and sports. , prepares for life and teaches military training. During the training, children's physical qualities are formed, along with functional development, patriotism, politeness, internationalism, hard work, and discipline are cultivated.

The work of a physical education teacher in physical education and sports consists of 2 independent parts - pedagogical and management activities. Work activities include: planning, organizing, conducting training, reporting and checking physical fitness, pedagogic, educational, sports and wellness work, student recruitment and selection, refereeing in sports competitions, organizational work, lectures, improving one's skills in financial affairs, etc.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Proving the high level of professional knowledge of a physical education specialist determines the content of the field as a complex functional basis. It not only expands in the process of communication, but also becomes more meaningful in its professional direction. Sufficiently formal activities can be used to improve students' professional skills (for example, studying instructional materials does not require a personal approach to the student). However, the pedagogical process aimed at improving professional skills implies a very informal action (that is, such a method of interaction in the subject-object system, in which its controlled element does not tend to be formalized).

Any human activity is determined and performed by its unique aspect. The diversity of conducting classes, the change of the conditions of conducting them, cannot have any effect on the teacher who conducts them. In physical education, it is not the same according to the contribution of training: the greater the range of movement activities of students in the hall, in the stadium, in the open air, the more difficult it is to control them, and the influence of the coach on the participants, the students, will be correctly directed.

It should be said that the requirement for the teacher is his main voice in management and communication (giving orders, calling for order, explaining, etc.)

Another special aspect affects to a certain extent: the activity of the teacher, the educational activity of the teachers, characterized by the high mobility of students. According to the curriculum, physical training is mandatory for students in educational institutions. The "Physical education" educational subject includes various physical and sports exercises and sports.

Therefore, the teacher must not only prepare his "technique" according to the program when learning the material, but he must always keep his technical and physical level high.

A physical education teacher should have many qualities: high efficiency; ability to ignore distractions and concentrate; always be active; know how to quickly renew high general and emotional tone, strength during the working day; distinguished by a clear interpretation of the idea; equality in the dynamics of emotions, keeping a high tempo in the performance of work; to quickly try to solve the problem without the exercise of writing muscle twitches; ability to quickly decide to switch from one type of activity to another; to have the ability to conduct training without prior preparation, to quickly get used to new conditions.

A high level of knowledge of a coach in the field of biological and psychological processes, during the period of active growth and development of a teenager, requires great physical and

technical training from a coach, especially to have pedagogical skills, according to the results of many studies and practices:

- to be able to convey the curriculum in a way that is understandable to the student, to have a scientific approach to the work process;
- having pedagogical qualities, the ability to attract all students, to work with a team;
- organization of a children's and teenagers' group, acquaintance with the life of students and interest in it;
- conducting conversations in an interesting and comprehensible manner, fluency in speech;
- observability, drawing correct conclusions by analyzing observations, being demanding towards students and oneself;
- to make the curriculum interesting by connecting it with the present time and life.

During the development of the professional skills of a physical education specialist, it is a self-growing personal size in leadership, the ability to choose the optimal options for relations with staff, resolve conflicts, and calmly take sides in certain situations.

RESULTS ANALYSIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In every task of a professional, an individual-personal style of activity is observed, and if the professional qualities of a professional can be conditionally included in the first group of important qualities specific to the profession, then the second group (more precisely, the second half) includes individual-personal qualities.

Requirements for the development of professional skills of physical education and sports specialists:

At the first level - reproducibility (minimum) exercises, the ability to perform them in a system or combinations, ability to demonstrate the ability to convey one's knowledge, regardless of theoretical and practical training.

At the second level - adaptation (low). The coach conveys what he knows not only in accordance with the competence and understanding of the individual aspects of his students.

At the third level - a local model (middle), not only able to convey his knowledge, the ability to adapt it to the aspects of young athletes, but also to construct (model) the system of knowledge and physical fitness, knowledge and skills in a physical, technical, tactical direction.

At the fourth level - knowledge modeled in the system (high). The coach knows how to model the activities of young athletes in the system, because he adapts the knowledge and skills he has acquired from the chosen sport to the knowledge system.

At the fifth level - systematically modeled activity and behavior (extremely high). The coach knows how to model such a system of sports training that shapes the athlete as a person, taking into account not only his physical, but also his mental and spiritual aspects. This leads to mental freshness and humanity at a high level, to achieve high sports results.

The conceptual model of the development of professional skills of a specialist in the field of physical education and sports management includes programmatic, goal-oriented, motivational-motivational diagnosis and pre-determining content. Based on them, meaningful and therapeutic-active content is formed, which is a meaningful structural element of the conceptual model.

A coach's knowledge and personal qualities improve in his practical work, if he can observe, analyze and draw correct conclusions. In order for this process to be effective, it is necessary to master the teaching methods of a certain system.

In the method of individualization of the professional skill development of physical education specialists, the contents identified as leaders by students, as well as individual-personal psychophysiological qualities (reactivity, psychoemotional stability, creative activity) were included.

Among the high needs that determine the level of professional skill and its development, there is also the need for work-related communication. Communication is included in the scope of communicative actions and participates in them as an effective means of realizing individual-personal qualities of an employee in the field of physical education and sports management.

It can be seen from the cited sources that the range of activities and professional commitment of a physical education teacher is creatively fulfilled by systematic preparation for higher physical education knowledge. Thus, in addition, the scope of the professional responsibility of the physical education teacher in schools and higher educational institutions is not less, where the teacher fulfills his pedagogical obligations in the same framework.

Based on the information given above, it can be concluded that the teacher's cheerfulness, kindness and humaneness lead the student to think that the teacher is empty in some cases. Therefore, the teacher must always be demanding.

CONCLUSION. In the initial stages of the development of professional skills, a physical education specialist is usually influenced by internal, reflexive, non-evaluable incentives and desires. The choice of a narrow professional activity is a purely reflexive phenomenon, that is, in sports, which is the most attractive form of self-expression, it is connected not only with the awareness of the need for personal improvement, but also with acquiring the skills to teach it to one's students. In other words, professional activity in the field of physical education has a reflexive, conscious instruction on its personal basis.

Professional communication of a physical education specialist is a communicative structure of knowledge, which includes mastering the norms of business communication specific to the chosen type of professional activity, for example, for an oriental martial arts coach - knowing special terms that sometimes have no equivalent in Russian, Uzbek. , to be able to establish business relations and cooperation, to arouse interest in one's work while ensuring competition in the labor market. The teacher should actively engage the students. In this case, students look at the teacher with affection. The behavior of the teacher, his coldness and rudeness have a negative effect on the student. Until the end of the student's childhood, the teacher and the student understand each other well. Pupils can give a good assessment of the teacher as a person.

The encouraging motivational structure of the professional skills development model was intended to develop students' cognitive activity and successful attempts to acquire professional skills. In the block of therapeutic activity, it was planned to regularly increase the level of professional knowledge in the field of education, to master the methods and forms of innovative activity in the field of physical education and sports.

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